

Increasing the impact of ecosystem services assessment with a novel national-level stakeholder consultation process: A case study from the Czech Republic

Jan Daněk^{1,*}, Kateřina Mácová², Bronislav Farkač^{1,2}, Davina Vačkářová^{1,2}

¹ Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Bělidla 986/4a, 603 00 Brno, Czech Republic

² Charles University, Environment Centre, José Martího 407/2, 160 00 Prague 6, Czech Republic

* Corresponding author, email: danek.j@czechglobe.cz

Abstract

There have been numerous calls to minimize the gap between ES knowledge and its implementation in policy, decision making, and practice, which reflect the mission-oriented nature of ecosystem services (ES) assessments. Engaging stakeholders in coproduction of knowledge and transdisciplinary approaches are suggested as promising means to deliver relevant, credible, and legitimate outcomes to increase the impact of ES assessments. We employed a novel stakeholder consultation process which aimed to increase the actual uptake of ES assessment.

We used a multimethod approach, applying stakeholder analysis, semistructured interviews, and participatory workshops. We gathered empirical data on the purpose of ES assessments and the settings of the forthcoming national platform, following the ultimate goal to increase the impact of ES assessment. A three-dimensional stakeholder matrix allowed us to select the key stakeholders to be involved in various stages of consultations. Stakeholders prioritized ES for assessment, with demand highest for regulating ES. They also highlighted perceived barriers, suitable areas for ES implementation, and factors influencing the uptake of the ES framework. Moreover, they provided specific examples of expected use and perceived barriers to use for the assessment of two ES: regulation of climate and physical and psychological experiences.

Mapping and engaging stakeholders and the knowledge coproduced allowed us to tailor the ES assessment to the needs of target users and facilitated the development of the National Platform for ES. We suggest that stakeholder consultations can help to address the gap between ES knowledge and its desirable application in policy, decision making, and practice.

Keywords

knowledge coproduction; implementation; nature's contributions to people; national platform; transdisciplinary research; Natura 2000 network

Highlights

- Consultations can address the gap between ES knowledge and implementation
- A three-dimensional matrix allowed to select key stakeholders for engagement
- Stakeholders mostly prioritized regulating ES for assessment
- The knowledge coproduced allowed to tailor the ES assessment to the needs of target users
- Consultations facilitated the development of the National Platform for ES

preprint

Introduction

Nature and ecosystems provide a range of benefits to people and society. These benefits can be conceptualized with ecosystem services (ES) or nature's contributions to people (NCP) frameworks, which allow for the analysis of human-nature relationships that affect and contribute to human well-being (MA, 2005; Costanza et al., 2017; IPBES, 2019). In general, ES frameworks facilitate ES assessments (Maund et al., 2020). One of the main goals of ES assessments is to enable more informed decision making about the use of nature and ecosystems (Blicharska and Hilding-Rydevik 2018), which should ultimately lead to more sustainable management of land, biodiversity, water, and other elements of natural capital (Daily et al., 2009). For example, the use of the ES framework can facilitate more transparent decision making and more efficient use of natural resources (Greenhalgh and Hart 2015) or enhance the resilience and sustainability of social-ecological systems (Schaefer et al., 2015; Sarkki et al., 2017).

Although the number of ES-related scientific publications continues to grow, the real-world application of ES knowledge still does not reflect the efforts of the scientific community to implement ES in decision making and practice (Keenan et al., 2019; Mandle et al., 2020). In-depth information on the impact on policy and decision making, e.g., how decision makers use ES knowledge, is still rather scarce (Posner et al., 2016; Saarikoski et al., 2018; Patenaude et al., 2019; Zolyomi et al., 2023). Nevertheless, a number of studies have emerged in recent years that explore the factors that influence the implementation of the ES framework in policy and decision making (e.g., Spangenberg et al., 2015; Wright et al., 2017; Ainscough et al., 2018; Dick et al., 2018; Saarikoski et al., 2018; De Vreese et al., 2019; Keenan et al., 2019; Mandle et al., 2020; Grunewald et al., 2021). Although it is possible to draw some general conclusions regarding the uptake of the ES framework (including barriers, challenges, success factors, etc.), it is vital to enhance the evidence from Central Europe, as the countries in this region possess particular institutional settings, knowledge cultures, or stakeholder perceptions different from Western European countries. In Central and Eastern Europe (CEE), there is limited trust in institutions combined with a shorter tradition and a lower appreciation of civic engagement (Nastran, 2015; Stringer & Paavola, 2013). This is often influenced by the recent history of the region (Grodzinska-Jurczak & Cent, 2011; Jehlička & Jacobsson, 2021). Additionally, social research on nature conservation in CEE countries, including the Czech Republic, is underrepresented in the literature (Blicharska et al., 2016; Young et al., 2018).

Theories that examine the relationship between science and policy emphasize the pivotal role of knowledge in its capacity to influence decision making (Posner et al., 2016; Carmen et al., 2018). It cannot be assumed that an increase in knowledge will automatically lead to better and more informed decision making (Saarikoski et al., 2018). Some researchers have therefore emphasized the importance of relevance in ES assessment, for example in the CRELE approach (Cash et al., 2003), which suggests credibility, relevance, and legitimacy as necessary conditions for a practical real impact (Wright et al., 2017). To increase the relevance of ES assessments for practical implementation, participatory approaches are of paramount importance (Cowling et al., 2008; Luyet et al., 2012; Durham et al., 2014;

Scemama et al., 2022). Participation and collaboration across different stakeholders in ES assessments can increase the possibilities of operationalizing the ES framework (Dick et al., 2018); it is a key element for achieving impact in policies (Zolyomi et al., 2023). Thus, increasing the relevance of ES research through stakeholder engagement can be the determining factor for the usefulness of the results and the extent to which they can contribute to the wider field of knowledge beyond the confines of academic exercises (Hansen et al., 2015; Barnaud et al., 2018). Additionally, the participation of stakeholders may serve a variety of objectives beyond the mere undertaking of an ES assessment (Malmborg et al., 2021; Scemama et al., 2022); it can also be used in building the ES science-policy interface. Although recommendations from the literature on stakeholder engagement in ES research exist (e.g., Spangenberg et al., 2015; Schoonover et al., 2019), researchers have rarely explored in detail specific roles and attributes of stakeholder analysis in ES research (e.g., Raum 2018). While the importance of stakeholder engagement in ES assessments is widely acknowledged, the context differs significantly from local to national, and also in the purposes or targeted ecosystems (c.f. Malmborg et al., 2021; Scemama et al., 2022).

In the Czech Republic, a few recent efforts to address ES implementation have focused on the perspective of assessing the status quo (Schneider and Kubíčková 2020; Grunewald et al., 2021; Daněk et al., 2023). Other recent studies have employed participatory approaches in ES assessment (e.g., Harmáčková et al., 2023; Daněk et al., under review) and thus contributed to increasing awareness of ES among various stakeholders and potentially also higher levels of impact (Posner et al., 2016). However, the previous efforts on ES assessment focused on a particular issue in a local or regional context, and without a specific focus on ES implementation or a national science-policy interface. In order to address these research gaps, we conducted a case study focused on the systematic engagement of Czech Natura 2000 network-related stakeholders in consultations concerning ES assessment and building a national science-policy interface, following the ultimate goal to increase the impact of ES assessment.

This study was part of the One Nature project (Integrated LIFE project for the Natura 2000 network in the Czech Republic) which aimed at, among others, assessing socioeconomic benefits (including ES) provided by protected areas. Natura 2000 is a network of protected areas aiming to protect habitats and species of European importance. It is made up of Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) and Special Protection Areas (SPAs) designated under the Habitats Directive and the Birds Directive, respectively. In the Czech Republic, there are 41 SPAs covering 703 437 ha and 1 112 SACs covering 795 640 ha. Totally, they cover 14 % of the Czech landscape (1 115 358 ha) as these areas can overlap. Also, they overlap with national parks and protected landscape areas and therefore, provide a wide array of benefits to society, including material, regulating and nonmaterial benefits (Daněk et al., 2023).

The main aims of the consultations were to tailor the forthcoming ES assessment to the needs of target users and to facilitate the establishment of institutionalized structure for continual engagement of key stakeholders in building the national science-policy interface - National Platform for Ecosystem Services (NPES). These stakeholders were potential

members of the upcoming NPES. To answer our aims, we apply participatory and transdisciplinary approaches to identify: a) stakeholder's attitudes towards ES (priorities, needs, knowledge, and experiences with ES); b) opportunities for implementation of the ES framework; c) inputs to design the NPES.

Methodology

Conceptual framework of consultations with stakeholders

In order to achieve research objectives, we conducted stakeholder analysis and engaged eligible stakeholders iteratively in interviews and workshops (Figure 1). The emphasis on specific objectives varies across different forms of consultations (interviews or workshops) and stages or rounds of consultations. The distinct stages and rounds of consultations build on one another, adapt to the findings of the previous stage, and thus work iteratively, beyond a simple linear process (Sarkki et al., 2015). Using the snowball method, each stage of consultations also served to add further relevant contacts to the stakeholder's database (Biernacki and Waldorf, 1981).

Figure 1: Workflow diagram of each method and their relationship within the process of consultations with stakeholders. Outputs from consultations (two boxes right) were used to: a) tailor the ES assessment to the needs of target users; b) create conditions for the establishment of a National Platform for Ecosystem Services (NPES).

The design of consultations was based on existing research on the engagement of stakeholders in research and its implementation. In particular, the CRELE approach helped to justify the need for consultations with a view to enhancing the validity and value of the upcoming ES assessment. Specifically, we wanted to start communication and negotiations with its potential users to ensure acceptance of research findings by key actors (Durham et al., 2014). At the same time, the consultations were aimed at setting up communication with potential members of the NPES. Thus, we placed particular importance on long-term effective actor engagement and followed recommendations by Schoonover et al. (2019), which propose that creating space, aligning motivations, and building trust are key elements to be considered. Furthermore, we followed recommended practices for actor engagement according to Luyet et al. (2012) to ensure the successful participation of stakeholders. Specifically for workshops, principles for cultivating communities of practice were applied,

namely an open dialogue of internal and external perspectives and a combination of familiarity and excitement (Metzger et al., 2019).

The concept of consultations draws on strategies for coproducing knowledge (Reed and Abernathy, 2018), namely knowledge translation and social learning. We understand knowledge translation as a synthesis, exchange, and application of knowledge of different actors (especially from researchers to practitioners and users of the results) in a common language and in such a way that the different actors are able to identify, understand, and use the results optimally and effectively for their purposes (Straus et al., 2011). Social learning allows individuals and groups with different knowledge, experiences, perspectives, values, and capacities to work together and, through iterative reflection, learn to better understand the challenges at the interface of the environment and human society and to deal with them (Borja et al., under review).

The framework of consultations was designed to enable social learning and coproduction of new knowledge (Reed and Abernathy, 2018), regarding a) the desired purpose, scope, procedures, methods, setting details, use, and communication of ES assessment results, including identification of possible overlaps or trade-offs between different evaluation purposes; b) the appropriate setting and functionality of the NPES as a platform for long-term collaboration on ES assessment and implementation across actors in the country, creating an enabling environment for innovation towards sustainable use of nature's benefits through the engagement of relevant actors.

To frame specific categories of benefits, we used the NCP framework according to Díaz et al. (2018). In interactions with actors, we used both "nature's contributions to people" and "ecosystem services" terms, as the latter showed to be more embedded in Czech discourse and was also a preferred term among actors. The interchangeable usage of the ES and NCP terms was also relevant, as we included only a generalizing perspective of NCP and focused our research only on positive contributions.

Stakeholder analysis

The analysis of stakeholders consisted of several steps (Figure 2). These activities were conducted iteratively, in several rounds, and were based on integrated stakeholder engagement methods (Gramberger et al., 2015) as well as on the method of analytical categorization of actors (see, e.g., Reed et al., 2009; Raum, 2018). Firstly, we delineated the context of the analysis by setting the boundaries and stating the clear purpose of this analysis (Reed et al., 2009) - creating a database of stakeholders operating at the national (alternatively regional) level in the Natura 2000 network. Due to the size of the Natura 2000 network, there are many individual actors (physical and legal persons) that interact with the Natura 2000 network or individual sites. Local actors often have very limited spatial relevance, and they change dynamically over time. Thus, an effective way to ensure the representation of all relevant types of stakeholders was to identify organizations (associations, societies, or unions) in which local stakeholders are organized, and which represent and promote their interests at the national or regional level.

Figure 2: Conceptual framework of stakeholder analysis presenting the main steps in the process of identification, evaluation and categorization of stakeholders.

The second step was to establish criteria on two levels. Eligibility criteria allowed us to include relevant actors in the database for further analysis. The focus was on actors who: a) were intended users of the results of the ES assessment; or b) significantly affect decision making or activities (and through that also ES) in Natura 2000 sites. For the purpose of prioritization between relevant actors, three evaluation criteria included: a) type of influence (direct or indirect); b) intensity of influence (high-medium-low); c) expected user of the ES assessment (yes or no). The criteria for evaluation follow the logic of "interest-influence" matrices (Reed et al., 2009) but are adjusted to the needs of this specific analysis, especially to increase the impact of the project results.

In the third step, a spreadsheet database was created and filled with stakeholders according to the criteria for inclusion. Iterative exploration of potential actors was conducted by the research team, representing two research institutions, and also by the Ministry of Environment (MoE) and the Nature Conservation Agency of the Czech Republic (NCA CR) as two key actors who are responsible for the establishment and management of Natura 2000 sites. As a control method for ensuring comprehensive coverage of relevant stakeholders, we triangulated the previous step using a list of stakeholders who were contacted in the process of establishing Natura 2000 sites in 2008; the list had been compiled by the NCA CR. Next, two expert panels (Martín-Lopez et al., 2019) were conducted to evaluate each actor in the database and also to add any other relevant actor who may have been missed in the previous steps of the analysis. These evaluation meetings were attended by 4–5 experts from the relevant institutions (MoE and NCA CR), who also provided further valuable information, e.g., for grouping or clustering actors.

Finally, a three-dimensional matrix was constructed for the purpose of analytically categorizing stakeholders (Raum, 2018). The matrix was populated with the stakeholders in question, who were categorized into groups according to the three evaluation criteria (type of influence, intensity of influence, and implementation potential).

Data collection

Semistructured interviews

In the second stage of the consultation process, we conducted semistructured interviews with representatives of key stakeholders. We followed a purposive sampling strategy (Bryman, 2016) and selected institutions that could be characterized as the "most

important” actors according to the results of the stakeholder analysis (actors with a high intensity of influence and with an implementation potential). Official representatives of the institution or staff with the greatest thematic overlap were recruited.

A total of 18 interviews were conducted between June and November 2020 – 10 interviews were conducted in person, and the remaining 8 were conducted online via a video call (due to the limitations of the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic). The first interview (with an NCA CR representative) was conducted as a pilot to evaluate the design and proposed questions. The length of the interviews ranged from 38 to 99 minutes. All interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed for analysis.

At the beginning of each interview, respondents were briefly introduced to the aims and process of the interview and provided with informed consent to participate in the research.¹ The interview protocol consisted of five parts: a) Self-identification of the actor in relation to Natura 2000; b) Perception and identification of NCP; c) Adaptation of the ES assessment to the needs of target users; d) NPES; e) Identification of other key actors (Appendix - interview protocol). During interviews, respondents were presented with the framework and classification of NCP according to Díaz et al. (2018), which was necessary for the subsequent prioritization of benefits (ES) for the assessment and also with different examples of ES assessments. For the NPES topic, respondents were presented with a summary of basic characteristics, expected aims, and organizational aspects of the platform. The interview format allowed us to focus on all three specific objectives of consultations (see section 2.1. Conceptual framework of consultations with stakeholders).

Participatory workshops

We conducted two rounds of online workshops due to the limitations of the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. We used a format similar to the focus group discussions (Slovák et al., 2023), i.e., shorter length and a smaller number of participants (7-8) compared to a standard face-to-face workshop (15-20 participants). A total of 6 workshops were conducted, the first round in November 2020 with 15 participants and the second round in May 2021 with 38 participants. For the first round of workshops, the same stakeholders were selected as those who participated in the interviews. For the second round, we aimed to include all remaining actors who were primary users of the ES assessment, regardless of their type or intensity of influence. The aim was therefore to invite as many relevant actors as possible to at least one workshop as representatives of institutions that would be primary users of the project outputs and have an influence on decision making or activities in the Natura 2000 network.

The workshops were focused on two specific objectives of the consultations – identifying attitudes towards ES and opportunities for ES framework implementation (Table 1). Similar to the interviews, the workshops elicited the needs of actors regarding the outcomes of ES assessment, but in a more detailed context for two specific ES categories – regulation of climate and physical and psychological experiences). In order to collect evidence on the

¹ The research was approved by the Ethical Board of the Charles University Environment Centre and conducted following the Ethical Codex of the Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences (internal directive n. 1/2017).

outcomes of the knowledge exchange process (Karcher et al., 2021), we extended an evaluation questionnaire to gather additional data regarding knowledge acquisition and learning and also implementation of the ES framework.

Table 1: Overview of the content of workshops.

Session	Themes and goals	Conceptual framings
Introduction	- Introduction of the One Nature project (including NPES) and the role of ES assessment	- Align understanding of the ES framework across actors (Schoonover et al., 2019)
ES framework and examples of ES assessment	- Introduction of the ES framework and categories - Exemplary detailed assessment for two ES - Activity 1 - questionnaire and discussion: Choosing the more relevant/applicable of the two ES presented, responding to the question: can it be used for any specific purpose - if so, what is it for; what are the barriers to its use, if any?	- Knowledge translation through framing (Schoonover et al., 2019) - Feedback to framework, previous experiences in use, barriers to use (Saarikoski et al., 2018) through an open dialogue of internal and external perspectives (Metzger et al., 2019)
Prioritization of ES for assessment	- Preliminary results of the previous stage of consultations (interviews) - Activity 2 - interactive exercise and discussion: Prioritization of the five most important ES for each participant separately, for which we would provide (detailed) values and justification for the choice - Group discussion of all participants on preferred ES and possible use of the ES assessment results	- The level of participation according to Luyet et al. (2012): Information - Consultation - Collaboration - Coproduction of knowledge regarding prioritization of ES for assessment (Reed and Abernethy, 2018) - Social learning (Reed and Abernethy, 2018)
Evaluation (ex-post)	- Self-assessed knowledge acquisition and learning	

We used the Zoom platform to facilitate video calls, supported by the Padlet platform to share workshop information with participants. Working material for participants with the ES framework and examples of categories was emailed to registered participants. The participatory parts included two activities, each building on the previous presentation. For the first activity, the Google Forms questionnaire ([google.com/forms](https://www.google.com/forms)) was used for voting and collecting qualitative and quantitative data. For the second activity, the participatory platform Mentimeter ([mentimeter.com](https://www.mentimeter.com)) was used to ask participants questions through an interactive presentation and to generate quantitative and qualitative data in real time. In the opening session of each webinar, participants were presented with organizational information and informed consent to participate in the research and recording of the webinar, followed by a brief introduction of the organizers and all participants.

Data analysis and interpretation

Semistructured interviews

The audio recordings of the interviews were transcribed verbatim and, together with the interviewees' notes, formed the data for the qualitative analysis using MAXQDA software ([maxqda.com](https://www.maxqda.com)). We used the method of directed content analysis (Hsieh and Shannon, 2005) with elements of thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006). First, the interview transcripts were coded with primary codes. In the next steps, these primary codes were grouped into larger-scale categories, and relationships between the categories were constructed (Saldaña, 2016). These categories were also theory-driven, e.g., for mentions of specific ES. At each

step, the categories were revised iteratively and compared with the primary codes to maintain the embeddedness of the analytic categories.

To assess the knowledge and experiences with ES, we looked for references about the use of the ES framework as part of the inductive content analysis. Similarly, we followed the inductive coding approach for perceived barriers and suitable areas for implementation of the ES framework, and also for themes related to the focus and format of the NPES.

To identify preferences for specific ES, we used a preference assessment and let respondents select an unlimited number of ES categories (17 total) with a guiding question: *“In order to make the project outputs (ES assessment) as useful as possible for you and your institution (or the actors it represents), which specific ES should we focus on?”*. We then counted the votes in the whole dataset and presented the results in a quantitative manner.

Participatory workshops

We collected both qualitative and quantitative data in the workshops. To identify preferences for specific ES, participants assessed the importance of developing assessments for the remaining 15 ES (i.e., all other ES except for the regulation of climate and physical and psychological experiences, which had already been for detailed assessment). In doing so, the question was set as selecting a maximum of five additional ES for assessment. The votes were then counted for all participants and presented in a graph. For the implementation of a specific ES assessment, we used the qualitative data from a freelist exercise and extracted themes related to the expected use of the results and perceived barriers as part of the inductive content analysis. Then, we counted the frequency of occurrence of the final codes, which reflects the saturation of the information in the dataset. The results are presented in a word cloud graph, which contains all mentioned themes and highlights those most frequently mentioned. Qualitative data from an ex-post evaluation questionnaire related to the ES framework implementation were analyzed in the same way, and results are presented in word cloud graphs.

Results

Stakeholder matrix

The results of stakeholder analysis are summarized in the matrix according to three evaluation criteria (type of influence – intensity of influence – implementation potential) (Figure 3). The most important key stakeholders are placed in the upper-left corner as they represent institutions with an important level of direct influence. They are also primary target users of ES assessment. These results suggested that an elevated level of involvement in the project is desirable and can be assumed ex-ante, allowing a range of participation levels (Information-Consultation-Collaboration according to Luyet et al., 2012) for these actors to be targeted. Thus, this group of stakeholders was selected for two stages of consultations (interviews and workshops), with an exception for regional-type institutions. Due to the considerable number of regional authorities, these were represented by the Association of Regions. Similarly, administrations of national parks as well as river basin management authorities were invited to participate in the workshops, as their format

allowed us to accommodate them all. An overview of stakeholders participating in the consultation process is shown in Table 2.

	High level of influence	Medium level of influence	Low level of influence
Direct influence + Primary user of ES assessment	Ministry of Environment Nature Conservation Agency of the Czech Republic Forests of the Czech Republic Military forests Ministry of Agriculture Ministry of Culture Union of Towns and Municipalities of the Czech Republic Agricultural Association of the Czech Republic Agrarian Chamber of Czech Republic Czech Fish Farmers Association The Association of Municipal, Private and Church Forest Owners in the Czech Republic Czech Society for Ornithology Czech Union for Nature Conservation Administrations of national parks (4) Regional authorities (14) River basin management authorities (5)	Ministry of Regional Development Ministry of Defense Ministry of Transport National Heritage Institute Association of Private Farming of the CR Czech-Moravian Association of Agricultural Entrepreneurs Association of Water Management of the Czech Republic Czech Association of Castle and Manor House Owners Confederation of Industry CZ The Czech Chamber of Commerce Arnika Military districts (4)	Czech Beekeepers Association Czech Landscape
	13 (23 regional)	11 (4 regional)	2
Direct influence	Czech-Moravian Hunting Union Czech Anglers Union Moravian Anglers Union	Cave Administration of the CR State Agricultural Intervention Fund The Czech Mining Authority Railway Administration Association of Sheep and Goat Breeders in the Czech Republic Czech Union of Beef Cattle Breeders The Young Agrarians' Society of the Czech Republic PRO-BIO Union of Organic Farmers Union of Marginal Areas	Union of Livestock Breeders Association of Landowners
	3	9	2
Indirect influence + Primary user of ES assessment	Association of Regions of the Czech Republic Hnutí DUHA - Friends of the Earth Czech Republic	CzechTourism Technology Agency of the Czech Republic Czech Chamber of Architects land associations (65)	Forest Management Institute State Land Office Institute of Agricultural Economics and Information Ministry of Finance Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports Ministry of Industry and Trade Czech Association of Forestry Entrepreneurs PEFC CZ FSC CZ Association of Water Managers of the CR ALKA Wildlife Beleco Green Circle Partnership foundation Spolek Ametyst Czech Botanical Society University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice Czech University of Life Sciences Prague Mendel University in Brno Charles University Masaryk University Palacký University Olomouc University of Ostrava J. E. P. University in Ústí nad Labem University of Hradec Králové Czech Academy of Sciences
	2	3 (65 regional)	26
Indirect influence		State Environmental Fund of the Czech Republic Czech Environmental Inspectorate The Road and Motorway Directorate of the Czech Republic	Office of the Government Office for Government Representation in Property Affairs Association of Local Authorities of the Czech Republic Czech Forestry Society control organisations for organic farming (4)
	0	3	4 (4 regional)

Figure 3: Key stakeholders in the three-dimensional matrix (type of influence – intensity of influence – implementation potential). The number in brackets shows the number of regional institutions.

Table 2: Overview of stakeholders participating in consultations.

Institution category	Interviews (No. of participants)	1 st round of workshops (No. of participants)	2 nd round of workshops (No. of participants)
Nature protection authorities, regional and local authorities	4	5	6
State administration and others	3	1	8
Agriculture, aquaculture	3	2	2
Forestry, hunting	4	5	3

NGOs	3	2	6
Universities, research	0	0	13
<i>Total number of participants</i>	<i>17</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>38</i>

Attitudes towards ES

Knowledge and experiences with ES

Results from interviews revealed that the majority of respondents were familiar with the ES framework, but not all had encountered it explicitly. Some were familiar with a similar approach specifically used in their field (e.g., nonproductive forest functions). About half of the respondents understood the ES framework mainly as an economic approach, where the value of services needs to be expressed in economic units. Using the monetary expression of ES, it would then be possible to talk in the language of economists: *“that we should learn to talk with economists, or try to talk with them in their language and try to evaluate the natural goods.”*

With one exception, respondents found the ES framework to be good and applicable to their practice. In one case, a respondent expressed concern about misuse of an ES assessment. Only a few respondents indicated that their institution used the ES framework in practice. This was mostly for use in conceptual documents as support for argumentation or in research projects. Two respondents stated that they had used the ES framework in the preparation of agricultural subsidy programs and measures or their ex-post evaluation in terms of their impact on selected ES. Another respondent from the forestry sector stated that they traditionally used the framework of nonproductive forest functions, which they perceived as: *“a certain subset of those ecosystem services.”* No respondent indicated that the ES framework was explicitly used in decision making.

Tailoring the ES assessment

The number of specific ES that interview respondents selected as priorities ranged from 3 to 14 out of a total of 17 categories. On average, each respondent selected 7 ES categories. Although respondents came from a variety of institutions with diverse backgrounds, their priorities were often similar (Figure 4a). Absolute agreement emerged on the regulation of water quantity and runoff (n=17), which was selected as a priority by all respondents. This was followed by three other regulatory ES, such as regulation of water quality (n=12), regulation of climate (n=10), and habitat creation and maintenance (n=9). Almost half of the respondents then selected physical and psychological experiences (n=8), which emerged as the most important nonmaterial benefit. Energy was the most significant of the material benefits (n=6).

Figure 4a: Prioritization of ES for assessment in interviews. Number of votes as an answer to the question: “Which specific ES should we focus on to make the outputs of the project (ES assessment) most useful to you and your institution (or the actors it represents)?” Respondents were asked to select an unlimited number of ES categories (17 total). Number of respondents: 17.

Figure 4b: Prioritization of ES for assessment in workshops. Number of votes as an answer to the question: “So far, two ES (regulation of climate, physical and psychological experiences) have been selected for detailed assessment and elaboration of the methodology. Which other ES (max. 5) should we focus on in the project to make the outputs as useful as possible for you and your institution in your practice?” Number of ES categories for voting: 15. Total number of votes: 215.

In workshops, the most frequently prioritized ES for assessment was regulation of water quantity and runoff (n=35), followed by other regulatory services such as habitat creation and maintenance (n=31) or formation, protection, and decontamination of soils (n=19) (Figure 4b). Maintenance of options was also very important (n=20). Although the results from different methods are not directly comparable, regulating ES was the most preferred group and material ES the least in both stages of consultations. Nonmaterial ES received somewhat average attention as a group with different results across various stages of consultations.

Opportunities for implementation of the ES framework

ES implementation – perceived barriers, suitable areas and factors influencing ES framework uptake

Interview respondents see the potential of using the ES framework in policies, legislation, decision-making practice, spatial planning, and decision making on landscape management practices (e.g., water management, forest management plans), or land use. Examples include water retention designs in the landscape or planning of water structures in terms of their impact on ES. Opportunities for the use of the ES framework are also found in

education, not only in schools but also in the general public and government, e.g., “So it can certainly be used from a practical point of view and especially for the awareness of the operational staff ... [in nature protection].”

In the economic understanding of the ES framework, interview respondents highlighted the possibilities of using it to evaluate the impact of subsidies on the ES or to introduce payments for ES (e.g., as additional nonproductive forest functions) that do not bring profit to the owner or land manager: “we want to see a system that will actually compensate for some of the burden on forest owners, that they have huge costs with the maintenance of forest roads, limiting their management ...” Another example would be the assessment of the bark beetle calamity in relation to the loss of ES: “some recovery of wood mass is quantified, but it is the loss of ecosystem services that is not quantified at all.”

A significant factor in the barriers to the possible use of the ES framework was the lack of capacity within institutions to introduce ES assessment into their agendas. Some respondents expressed concern about the “economization” and possible commodification of services – some services may be valued in inadequate units, or economic valuation could lead to the “economization” of services that they believe have no economic value and cannot be monetized. Another obstacle is the complexity of quantifying some services or the inconsistency of approaches to evaluation, with different types of evaluation giving different results: “the differences are of course from just a few million to x of billions when quantifying those agricultural activities.” Other obstacles mentioned in the interviews were inconsistency with the valid legislation (in forestry), a lack of awareness of the staff carrying out the actual management, or a potential misuse of an assessment.

The workshops allowed us to collect data on suitable policy areas for ES implementation from a broader range of stakeholders. The most frequently mentioned was that all areas of policy, decision making, or practice should use the ES framework (n=6) (Figure 5a). The second most frequently mentioned were agriculture (n=4) and spatial planning (n=4), followed by water management (n=3), agricultural subsidies (n=3) and policies (n=3). Overall, the group of agriculture-related themes had the most mentions and thus presented a primary area for ES implementation. There was no response that the ES framework should not be used, but a few respondents (n=3) mentioned that they could not think of any specific area.

Figure 5a: Word cloud presenting coded areas for implementing the ES framework as an answer to the question: “Can you think of any areas (policy, decision making, practice) that should or should not use the ES framework? If so, which ones and why?” The size of the text shows the frequency of each code, with a maximum frequency of 6 for the code “All areas”. The color of the text does not reflect the frequency or importance of each code. Number of respondents: 20.

Figure 5b: Word cloud presenting coded answers to the question: “What would have to change in order to (more or better) implement the ES framework in your practice?” The size of the text reflects the frequency of occurrence of codes; the maximum frequency is 12 for “Raise awareness for the public”. Number of respondents: 26.

Regarding specific conditions that could facilitate the implementation of the ES framework, the most frequently mentioned factor was better public awareness (n=12) (Figure 5b). Professional awareness (n=6) as well as the existence of methodologies for ES assessment (n=3) were also considered important prerequisites by workshop participants.

Assessment of specific ES – expected use of the results and perceived barriers

Nearly all participants (49 out of 50) could imagine how they would be able to use in their practice the results of an ES assessment (regulation of climate or physical and psychological experiences). For climate regulation, the most frequently mentioned theme was the use of arguments for protection (n=6) (Figure 6a), e.g., “anthropocentric explanation of the reason for the existence of protected areas to lay people.” Specifically, protected areas were also linked to climate change: “The contribution of [nature] reserves not only to biodiversity conservation but also to climate protection.” The assessment of climate regulation could further clarify the influence of the type of management (n=2), as well as the impacts of various plans or strategies on ES (n=2). In discussions, participants clarified that the application of the ES framework in the area of climate regulation can be a useful complement to the emphasis on emission reductions in the public debate – it can show how specific measures can be beneficial for carbon sequestration through the lens of the ES framework.

Figure 6a,b: Word clouds presenting coded answers to the question, "Can you imagine using this type of assessment for a specific purpose? Please briefly write 1-3 possible uses of the assessment for the selected ES." The size of the text reflects the frequency of occurrence of codes. Figure 6a Regulation of climate: maximum frequency is 6 for the code "Arguments for Protection". Number of respondents: 22. Figure 6b Physical and psychological experiences: maximum frequency is 5 for "Regulation of visitors". Number of respondents: 25.

Figure 6c,d: Word clouds presenting coded answers to the question, "Do you perceive any barriers to implementation of the ES assessment presented in your practice?" The size of the text reflects the frequency of occurrence of codes. Figure 6c Regulation of climate: maximum frequency is 5 for "Data availability". Number of respondents: 17. Figure 6d Physical and psychological experiences: maximum frequency is 3 for "Data availability" and "Effects of other factors". Number of respondents: 21.

For the physical and psychological experiences, the most frequently mentioned theme was visitor regulation (n=5) (Figure 6b), e.g., "Trying to better distribute visitors in the NP" or in relation to "Site limits - setting visitor levels = increasing the sustainability of the site." The assessment of such assessment could be used to set the management of the site (n=3) or as arguments for conservation (n=2): "Health and mental/aesthetic benefits ... allow to communicate broadly (from the position of a governmental authority) the meaningfulness of nature conservation in general and in specific areas and are understandable to the wider public as well as to e.g. local governments or businesses involved in the service sector." During the discussions, the participants suggested broadening the outdoor recreation indicator and also considering the impact on health. In terms of visitor regulation and the setting of area management, it was emphasized that these topics are related to the current issue of overtourism pressure on natural areas. In the context of the argument for conservation, they mentioned that the ES framework can be useful in communicating with the general public and specifically with local communities, municipalities, or tourism entrepreneurs to achieve sustainable tourism.

In terms of perceived barriers to using an assessment of the regulation of climate, participants most frequently mentioned the availability of good quality data (n=5) and the difficulty of conducting the assessment itself (n=4) (Figure 6c). More prominent in the responses was also the concern about acceptance of the ES framework (n=2): *“the approach using ES will probably need to be explained and defended as professionally robust to the public”*; and the need to consider the impact of farming or management on ES (n=2): *“The framework does not take into account the actual land management (activities contributing to sequestration - no-till technologies and vice versa).”* In the discussion, participants often mentioned that these barriers are intertwined – the low availability of good quality or sufficiently detailed data and the difficulty of assessment can produce less credible figures, which reduces the overall acceptance of the assessment and the ES framework.

In terms of perceived barriers to the use of an assessment of physical and psychological experiences, participants most frequently mentioned issues related to the availability of data (n=3): *“Input data itself - only for a small part of the Czech Republic can such an evaluation be supported by exact data”* and effects of other factors that make the assessment incomplete (n=3), *“The assessment does not take into account the accessibility of the territory, proximity to cities, or, on the contrary, remoteness”* (Figure 6d). Some participants then expressed concerns about the data accuracy and the relevance of ES to existing policies: *“the central government forest management authority (Ministry of Agriculture) perceives sustainable forest management as management under the existing forest law, where so-called nonproductive services are provided spontaneously”* or land consolidation processes. In contrast to climate regulation, several participants here indicated (n=3) that they did not see any barriers to using an assessment of physical and psychological experiences in practice.

Focus and format of the National Platform for Ecosystem Services

The establishment of the NPES was identified by many respondents as a welcome step to better inform each other and to be able to discuss points of view, e.g., to find out or understand the other side’s position: *“Well, it’s always useful to know what the other side thinks.”* Respondents identified a number of specific themes and objectives that they felt the NPES should work towards, as well as a number of recommendations for the format and breadth of its focus or representation of different actors.

One of the objectives of the NPES could be to spread awareness about ES and to support the implementation of the ES framework. The ES framework could be used in policy assessments and other strategic issues or directly as a basis for the development of strategies: *“Well, the exchange of information is definitely the basis.... But, in principle it should be directed towards, for example, the platform contributing towards the formulation of some proposal, how and what to include in strategic documents, for example - to identify some directions.”* Respondents also see the potential of the NPES in the future development of protected areas, e.g., *“the future development of Natura, some kind of expansion or timetable, and how the Ministry of Environment sees that the activities should develop.”* An important related topic is nature conservation legislation. The NPES could provide scope for proposals for amendments to Act 114/1992 Coll. and help to unify nature conservation legislation

across sectors. Another topic is the development of ES assessment methodologies that could contribute to the establishment of standard procedures for the state administration, especially nature conservation authorities.

Several actors representing owners or land managers see the NPES as an appropriate space to discuss payments for ES or compensations for certain management constraints resulting from nature conservation. *“From our point of view, speaking for landowners, there is certainly a need for better information and more respect from society as a whole that farmers, whether they are foresters, fishers, or others, are actually “sacrificing” themselves at the cost of the restrictive measures that, yes, protecting nature brings. Basically, they bear the burden. If this platform is created, I would like to see that it helps make this awareness even more respected and appreciated in society.”* From the point of view of farmers, it would also be useful to discuss some ES-related subsidy instruments and the setting of economic instruments. Other topics suitable for discussion within the NPES included river protection and water management in protected areas, or energy and climate change.

The set-up of the NPES can draw on many other recommendations based, inter alia, on the experience of actors from other similar platforms. In addition to the frequently mentioned independent position of the NPES organizer, respondents emphasized, for example, clear rules and narrowly defined objectives, achievable outcomes, and the responsiveness and effectiveness of the meetings. In terms of the representation of diverse types of actors, it is desirable to maintain a balance between them and to promote respectful communication. Respondents see the point of NPES not only at the national level but also when focusing regionally on certain topics or demonstrating solutions to a specific problem at the local level.

Social learning and knowledge transfer in participatory workshops

According to feedback from participants, the webinars provided them with new insights into ES, both from the workshop organizers and other participants in the discussions (Figure 7a). Assuming that social learning occurs when stakeholders learn something from each other during discussions, approx. 84% of respondents reported such acquisition of new information. Similarly, approx. 85% of respondents reported that the webinars helped them to understand how other actors perceive ES (Figure 7b). From the verbal responses, we noted a number of positive comments about the innovative use of online platforms, but also an interest in a longer face-to-face meeting of participants to *“get a more in-depth idea of who is doing what and what they are struggling with”* and to *“develop more in-depth project discussion”* or to exchange experiences about participants’ current ES-focused projects. Thus, despite the limiting conditions of the online webinar format of the meeting, it was possible to start a meaningful exchange of different perspectives on ES both in the form of knowledge transfer from organizers and also as a social learning process among participants.

Figure 7a: Responses to the question “Did you learn anything new or interesting during the webinar?” Number of respondents: 38.

Figure 7b: Responses to the question “Would you say that the webinar: ...” (see questions in chart). Number of respondents: 28.

Discussion

The stakeholder analysis was the key element in our participatory approach to increasing the impact of ES assessments and setting up the communication of these results across stakeholders so that they can be better integrated into their decision-making practices and policies affecting the Natura 2000 network. To maximize its benefits throughout consultations and reflect evolution in some sectors, it should be seen as a continuous process rather than a single activity (Raum 2018). Therefore, we also employed the consultations for informing the process of establishing the NPES, as an institutionalized long-term structure for increasing the impact of ES assessments. We conform with Durham et al. (2014), who suggest that the CRELE approach should also be applied to the process of stakeholder engagement. Such credible engagement should have clear objectives, use appropriate methods, and focus on continuity to maintain relationships and build trust. Relevant engagement emphasizes the usefulness of its process and outcomes and is linked to aligning understanding among different stakeholders. Finally, a fair and balanced inclusion of various groups of stakeholders can enhance the legitimacy of the process. We acknowledge a potential trade-off between relevance and legitimacy stemming from the fact that the experts for the evaluation of stakeholders were from state nature protection authorities (MoE and NCA CR). Nevertheless, our iterative engagement of the group of the most important actors proved successful, as they remained interested in further participation related to the establishment of the national platform. The iterative aspect of engagement in an emerging science-policy interface can play a significant role in determining its success (Sarkki et al., 2015; Spangenberg et al., 2015).

Our key actors perceive the ES framework as a promising and useful approach, but the results confirm that there is a significant gap between its perceived potential and its actual use in decision making or practice. Similar findings about the implementation of the ES framework were reported from managers of large-scale protected areas (Daněk et al., 2023) and thus suggest a broader scale issue in the Czech context. The understanding of the ES as only an economic framework among many stakeholders is still a prevalent myth to be

addressed (Ainscough et al., 2019), as it brings a need for raising awareness and developing a collective understanding of what an ES framework is and what possibilities it conveys beyond the economic perspective.

Prioritization of ES for assessment provided valuable information regarding which ES are potentially most useful for stakeholders as well as the desired purpose, scope, and details of an ES assessment. Overall, regulating ES were the most sought-after and confirmed their key role in the range of benefits provided by protected areas (see also Daněk et al., 2023). We suggest that a coproduction of knowledge regarding the prioritization of ES for assessment can enhance the relevance and legitimacy of the assessment and bring a sense of ownership (Malmborg et al., 2021), ultimately leading to a greater impact. Regardless of the specific purpose of stakeholder consultations, they emerge as an effective approach to support ES assessments (Scemama et al., 2022).

Stakeholders mentioned a broad range of areas suitable for implementation of the ES framework, with the agriculture sector being among the most referred to. These results confirm the multirelevance of the ES framework in many areas and the related need to include a broad range of stakeholders in a science-policy interface. The factor that, according to stakeholders, has the biggest effect in facilitating ES uptake is raising awareness for the public as well as for practitioners and policymakers. Different findings were reported from an Australian context where better measurement and reporting, communication, and incentives were identified as key solutions for increased ES adoption (Keenan et al., 2019). In a range of (mostly) European case studies, multistakeholder collaboration and coproduction of knowledge were identified as key enabling factors in the use of ES knowledge (Carmen et al., 2018; Saarikoski et al., 2018), further confirming the key role of stakeholder engagement.

Regarding the expected use of the results for two selected ES (regulation of climate and physical and psychological experiences), many specific uses of such an assessment were mentioned. The most frequently mentioned were additional arguments for (nature) protection and a tool to better distribute or regulate visitors. Ultimately, such a form of ES implementation could help in addressing global challenges such as climate change and biodiversity conservation (Congreve and Cross, 2019). Regarding perceived barriers to the implementation of such assessments, limited data availability was the most prominent response for both ES. Many other barriers were related to data and methodology and thus present important insights for future ES-related endeavors, especially valuable in connection with specific ES categories. Similar findings regarding methodological inconsistency and difficulty of assessment were already reported in other studies (e.g., Blicharska and Hilding-Rydevik, 2018; Tusznió et al., 2020; Daněk et al., 2023). Although institutional and communication-based issues (c.f. Saarikoski et al., 2018) were also present, they did not appear as major barriers. Interestingly, a lack of capacities was mentioned as a major barrier only in the interviews but not when referring to a specific ES assessment. This suggests that more specific prompts about the implementation of a particular ES, which also include a detailed presentation of an assessment approach and allow an exchange of perspectives, can bring different, more detailed, and potentially more valuable results. For example,

stakeholders emphasized the intertwined nature of some barriers, which can ultimately affect the credibility of results.

One of the reasons for the low uptake of the ES framework can be a mismatch between the ES theory and how actors actually think about nature (social representation of nature) (De Vreese et al., 2019). Therefore, we suggest that the need to develop a collective understanding of the ES framework across actors (Carmen et al., 2018) is an important prerequisite for the successful coproduction of useful ES knowledge. Thus, consultations were designed to help navigate the ES framework and specific groups and categories of ES, so the actors were provided with an essential knowledge base for mutual understanding. Related to developing a common language across stakeholders is the ability of the ES framework to play the role of a transdisciplinary boundary object (Abson et al., 2014; Schleyer et al., 2017; Carmen et al., 2018), which makes it possible to involve not only different experts but also other actors, including the public, in jointly addressing environmental problems. This allows actors to overcome the traditional narrow focus of sectors or disciplines, e.g., in the context of transdisciplinary research (Nesshöver et al., 2016) or improve the collaboration of actors at the science-policy interface within a purposefully designed 'boundary' organization (Honeck et al., 2021).

The information on developing a national platform for ES was well received by all prompted stakeholders, and they all expressed an interest in participation. The need for an institutionalized science-policy interface on ES research and its application was obvious, and it emerged in many forms – from an information exchange or raising awareness to an environment for discussing specific ES-related issues such as ES assessment methodologies, payments for ES, or nature conservation legislation. The neutral position of the platform organizer and a balanced representation of actors were among the key recommendations for its successful operation, potentially having a significant effect on perceived legitimacy (Wagner et al., 2024). Some aspects of the NPES and the antecedent consultations, such as a transdisciplinary community around the science-policy-practice of ES, are in line with the concept of communities of practice (Wenger et al., 2002; Metzger et al., 2019).

Reflecting the knowledge exchange (Karcher et al., 2021) in workshops, stakeholders positively evaluated both the usefulness of the information they learned from the researchers (knowledge translation) and the usefulness of the information they learned from other participants during discussions (social learning). Thus, within the limits of the online platform used, we successfully started the social learning process (c.f. Metzger et al., 2019). We suggest that an iterative social learning approach can enhance the process of stakeholder engagement as it promotes understanding of other actors' worldviews, builds trust across consultation participants, and can lead to a gradual change in norms and values (Sarkki et al., 2015; Eriksson et al., 2019). For the purpose of cocreating new knowledge and building a long-term relationship based on mutual dialogue and trust between researchers and policy and practice actors, it is important that, as the expected users of research results, stakeholders are systematically included from the very outset of a research project (Reed et al., 2014; Metzger et al., 2019). Furthermore, stakeholder engagement in the coproduction

of ES knowledge can provide useful input for addressing today's complex sustainability challenges (Schleyer et al., 2017; Norstrom et al., 2020).

Although participatory approaches do convey a range of limits and challenges (c.f. Luyet et al., 2012; Schoonover et al., 2019), it seems important to look for ways to increase the use of participatory reasoning about nature's values and to seek future pathways within existing sociocultural and institutional barriers (Saarikoski et al., 2018). The participatory research leading to the establishment of the NPES represents a major achievement in building the science-policy interface through an iterative process of consultations (see also Ruckelshaus et al., 2015; Norstrom et al., 2020) and the inclusion of a wide range of actors at the national level (including those with legislation- and policymaking powers). As such, it is a potentially very ambitious project that can support the implementation of the ES framework at various levels of policymaking and decision making in the country. Regarding the impact of our consultation process, we suggest that an attributional impact (Patenaude et al., 2019) or a conceptual and strategic use of ES knowledge was achieved (Posner et al., 2016). Moreover, the establishment of the NPES (4/10/2022) by the MoE could be considered an instrumental use as it turns the participatory consultation outputs into an institutionalized national science-policy platform.

Conclusions

The issue of implementing the ES framework is a very complex phenomenon that is still characterized by significant knowledge gaps. It certainly goes beyond just looking for the 'right' knowledge, as it represents a context-dependent, multistakeholder, dynamic process in the interplay of scientists, policymakers, and practitioners. In this context, this study provides important empirical evidence in two respects.

Firstly, it documents the multimethod approach of iterative participatory involvement of stakeholders that was designed to enhance the implementation of the ES assessment framework in practice and that successfully led to the establishment of a national ES platform in the Czech Republic. The methodology employed in this study may serve as a model for good practice in other case studies. Secondly, the study brings evidence on the attitudes and perceptions of a large and diverse set of Czech stakeholders towards ES, barriers and opportunities for implementation of the ES framework, and recommendations for the design of a national ES platform (NPES). Such information can help to increase the impact of future ES research as well as help stakeholders navigate the complex world of ES assessments and their implementation. Furthermore, the consultations were an important first step (on a national level) in engaging stakeholders and raising their awareness, which continued in further meetings of the NPES.²

This study corroborates the general understanding that, while some of the challenges and barriers to the wider application of the ES framework are potentially soluble by scientists alone, the majority can only be addressed through the involvement of stakeholders. In our case, the analysis of stakeholders and their engagement constituted an essential preliminary

² At the time of writing this article, there were three meetings of the NPES in the years 2022-2024.

step for increasing the societal relevance of ES assessments and ensuring their sustainability in the Czech Republic. The role of the newly inaugurated Czech national ES platform (NPES) as a science-policy interface will be further elucidated in due course. It is anticipated that this entity will assume a more prominent position in this endeavor of minimizing the existing gap between scientific ES knowledge and its desirable application in policy, decision making, and practice.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to all participants in the consultations (interviews, workshops) for sharing their valuable insights, as well as to the representatives of the MoE and NCA CR who provided consultations on the stakeholder analysis. This research was supported by the European Commission (grant number LIFE17 IPE/CZ/00005 – Integrated LIFE project for the Natura 2000 network in the Czech Republic) and by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic (grant AdAgriF – Advanced methods of greenhouse gases emission reduction and sequestration in agriculture and forest landscape for climate change mitigation CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004635). We would like to thank Johana Drlíková, Vojtěch Kračmar, Simona Zvěřinová, Jana Osúchová, David Stella, and Ivana Žížalová for help with data collection and processing.

Data Availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

References

Abson, D.J., Von Wehrden, H., Baumgärtner, S., Fischer, J., Hanspach, J., Härdtle, W., Heinrichs, H., Klein, A.M., Lang, D.J., Martens, P., Walmsley, D., 2014. Ecosystem services as a boundary object for sustainability. *Ecological Economics* 103, 29–37.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2014.04.012>

Ainscough, J., De Vries Lentsch, A., Metzger, M., Rounsevell, M., Schröter, M., Delbaere, B., De Groot, R., Staes, J., 2019. Navigating pluralism: Understanding perceptions of the ecosystem services concept. *Ecosystem Services* 36, 100892.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.01.004>

Barnaud, C., Corbera, E., Muradian, R., Salliou, N., Sirami, C., Vialatte, A., Choisis, J.-P., Dendoncker, N., Mathevet, R., Moreau, C., Reyes-García, V., Boada, M., Deconchat, M., Cibien, C., Garnier, S., Maneja, R., Antona, M., 2018. Ecosystem services, social interdependencies, and collective action: a conceptual framework. *E&S* 23, art15.

<https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-09848-230115>

Biernacki, P., Waldorf, D., 1981. Snowball Sampling: Problems and Techniques of Chain Referral Sampling. *Sociological Methods & Research* 10, 141–163.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/004912418101000205>

Blicharska, M., Hilding-Rydevik, T., 2018. "A thousand flowers are flowering just now" – Towards integration of the ecosystem services concept into decision making. *Ecosystem Services* 30, 181–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.03.001>

Blicharska, M., Orlikowska, E.H., Roberge, J.-M., Grodzinska-Jurczak, M., 2016. Contribution of social science to large scale biodiversity conservation: A review of research about the Natura 2000 network. *Biological Conservation* 199, 110–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2016.05.007>

Borja, D., Daněk, J., Assis, J., Gorosabel, A., Lundquist, C. J., Rosa, I. M. D., Scarano, F. R., Amazonas, N. T., Principe, S. C., Alkemade, R., Arshad, A., Gordillo, S. B., Lembi, R. C., Chagas, T. R. F., Clavijo, D., Cornejo-Denman, L. A., Dib, V., Ferrier, S., Lima, E. M., Lopes, L. F., Mancini, M. C. S., Martínez-Lanfranco, J. A., Moya, W., Niemeyer, J., Pascual, U., de Moraes, A. R., Salami, M. F., Rivera-Rebella, C., Sanches, F. H. C., Sarkar, P., Siqueira-Gay, J., Vieira, R. R. S., Rodríguez, C. Z., Joly, C. A., Borges, R. Rethinking Scenario Building for Sustainable Futures: Mobilizing Conscientização, Social Learning, and Knowledge Co-production. UNDER REVIEW in *Ecosystems and People*.

Braun, V., Clarke, V., 2006. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology* 3, 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>

Bryman, A., 2016. *Social research methods*, Fifth Edition. ed. Oxford University Press, Oxford ; New York.

Carmen, E., Watt, A., Carvalho, L., Dick, J., Fazey, I., Garcia-Blanco, G., Grizzetti, B., Hauck, J., Izakovicova, Z., Kopperoinen, L., Liqueste, C., Odee, D., Steingröver, E., Young, J., 2018. Knowledge needs for the operationalisation of the concept of ecosystem services. *Ecosystem Services* 29, 441–451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.10.012>

Cash, D.W., Clark, W.C., Alcock, F., Dickson, N.M., Eckley, N., Guston, D.H., Jäger, J., Mitchell, R.B., 2003. Knowledge systems for sustainable development. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 100, 8086–8091. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1231332100>

Congreve, A., Cross, I.D., 2019. Integrating ecosystem services into environmental decision-making. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 56, 494–499. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13341>

Costanza, R., De Groot, R., Braat, L., Kubiszewski, I., Fioramonti, L., Sutton, P., Farber, S., Grasso, M., 2017. Twenty years of ecosystem services: How far have we come and how far do we still need to go? *Ecosystem Services* 28, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.09.008>

Cowling, R.M., Egoh, B., Knight, A.T., O'Farrell, P.J., Reyers, B., Rouget, M., Roux, D.J., Welz, A., Wilhelm-Rechman, A., 2008. An operational model for mainstreaming ecosystem services for implementation. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 105, 9483–9488. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0706559105>

Daily, G.C., Polasky, S., Goldstein, J., Kareiva, P.M., Mooney, H.A., Pejchar, L., Ricketts, T.H., Salzman, J., Shallenberger, R., 2009. Ecosystem services in decision making: time to deliver. *Frontiers in Ecol & Environ* 7, 21–28. <https://doi.org/10.1890/080025>

Daněk, J., Blättler, L., Leventon, J., Vačkářová, D., 2023. Beyond nature conservation? Perceived benefits and role of the ecosystem services framework in protected landscape areas in the Czech Republic. *Ecosystem Services* 59, 101504.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2022.101504>

Daněk, J., Slovák, L., Daněk, T., Pánek, J., Schlossarek, M., & Blättler, L. Why do people go to nature? Enhancing the visibility and scope of perceived cultural ecosystem services in landscape. UNDER REVIEW in *People and Nature*.

De Vreese, R., Van Herzele, A., Dendoncker, N., Fontaine, C.M., Leys, M., 2019. Are stakeholders' social representations of nature and landscape compatible with the ecosystem service concept? *Ecosystem Services* 37, 100911.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.100911>

Díaz, S., Pascual, U., Stenseke, M., Martín-López, B., Watson, R.T., Molnár, Z., Hill, R., Chan, K.M.A., Baste, I.A., Brauman, K.A., Polasky, S., Church, A., Lonsdale, M., Larigauderie, A., Leadley, P.W., Van Oudenhoven, A.P.E., Van Der Plaats, F., Schröter, M., Lavorel, S., Aumeeruddy-Thomas, Y., Bukvareva, E., Davies, K., Demissew, S., Erpul, G., Failler, P., Guerra, C.A., Hewitt, C.L., Keune, H., Lindley, S., Shirayama, Y., 2018. Assessing nature's contributions to people. *Science* 359, 270–272. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aap8826>

Dick, J., Turkelboom, F., Woods, H., Iniesta-Arandia, I., Primmer, E., Saarela, S.-R., Bezák, P., Mederly, P., Leone, M., Verheyden, W., Kelemen, E., Hauck, J., Andrews, C., Antunes, P., Aszalós, R., Baró, F., Barton, D.N., Berry, P., Bugter, R., Carvalho, L., Czúcz, B., Dunford, R., Garcia Blanco, G., Geamănă, N., Giucă, R., Grizzetti, B., Izakovičová, Z., Kertész, M., Kopperoinen, L., Langemeyer, J., Montenegro Lapola, D., Liqueste, C., Luque, S., Martínez Pastur, G., Martin-Lopez, B., Mukhopadhyay, R., Niemela, J., Odee, D., Peri, P.L., Pinho, P., Patrício-Roberto, G.B., Preda, E., Priess, J., Röckmann, C., Santos, R., Silaghi, D., Smith, R., Vădineanu, A., Van Der Wal, J.T., Arany, I., Badea, O., Bela, G., Boros, E., Bucur, M., Blumentrath, S., Calvache, M., Carmen, E., Clemente, P., Fernandes, J., Ferraz, D., Fongar, C., García-Llorente, M., Gómez-Baggethun, E., Gundersen, V., Haavardsholm, O., Kalóczkai, Á., Khalalwe, T., Kiss, G., Köhler, B., Lazányi, O., Lellei-Kovács, E., Lichungu, R., Lindhjem, H., Magare, C., Mustajoki, J., Ndege, C., Nowell, M., Nuss Girona, S., Ochieng, J., Often, A., Palomo, I., Pataki, G., Reinvang, R., Rusch, G., Saarikoski, H., Smith, A., Soy Massoni, E., Stange, E., Vågnes Traaholt, N., Vári, Á., Verweij, P., Vikström, S., Yli-Pelkonen, V., Zulian, G., 2018. Stakeholders' perspectives on the operationalisation of the ecosystem service concept: Results from 27 case studies. *Ecosystem Services* 29, 552–565.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.09.015>

Eriksson, M., Van Riper, C.J., Leitschuh, B., Bentley Brymer, A., Rawluk, A., Raymond, C.M., Kenter, J.O., 2019. Social learning as a link between the individual and the collective: evaluating deliberation on social values. *Sustain Sci* 14, 1323–1332.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-019-00725-5>

Durham, E., Baker, H., Smith, M., Moore, E., Morgan, V., 2014. The BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook. BiodivERsA, Paris. [http://refhub.elsevier.com/S2212-0416\(15\)30031-0/sbref24](http://refhub.elsevier.com/S2212-0416(15)30031-0/sbref24)

Gramberger, M., Zellmer, K., Kok, K., Metzger, M.J., 2015. Stakeholder integrated research (STIR): a new approach tested in climate change adaptation research. *Climatic Change* 128, 201–214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-014-1225-x>

Greenhalgh, S., Hart, G., 2015. Mainstreaming ecosystem services into policy and decision-making: lessons from New Zealand's journey. *International Journal of Biodiversity Science, Ecosystem Services & Management* 11, 205–215. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21513732.2015.1042523>

Grodzinska-Jurczak, M., Cent, J., 2011. Expansion of Nature Conservation Areas: Problems with Natura 2000 Implementation in Poland? *Environmental Management* 47, 11–27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-010-9583-2>

Grunewald, K., Bastian, O., Louda, J., Arcidiacono, A., Brzoska, P., Bue, M., Cetin, N.I., Dworczyk, C., Dubova, L., Fitch, A., Jones, L., La Rosa, D., Mascarenhas, A., Ronchi, S., Schlaepfer, M.A., Sikorska, D., Tezer, A., 2021. Lessons learned from implementing the ecosystem services concept in urban planning. *Ecosystem Services* 49, 101273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2021.101273>

Hansen, R., Frantzeskaki, N., McPhearson, T., Rall, E., Kabisch, N., Kaczorowska, A., Kain, J.-H., Artmann, M., Pauleit, S., 2015. The uptake of the ecosystem services concept in planning discourses of European and American cities. *Ecosystem Services* 12, 228–246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.11.013>

Harmáčková, Z.V., Blättler, L., Aguiar, A.P.D., Daněk, J., Krpec, P., Vačkářová, D., 2022. Linking multiple values of nature with future impacts: value-based participatory scenario development for sustainable landscape governance. *Sustain Sci* 17, 849–864. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-00953-8>

Honeck, E., Gallagher, L., Von Arx, B., Lehmann, A., Wyler, N., Villarrubia, O., Guinaudeau, B., Schlaepfer, M.A., 2021. Integrating ecosystem services into policymaking – A case study on the use of boundary organizations. *Ecosystem Services* 49, 101286. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2021.101286>

Hsieh, H.-F., Shannon, S.E., 2005. Three Approaches to Qualitative Content Analysis. *Qual Health Res* 15, 1277–1288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732305276687>

IPBES. (2019). Summary for policymakers of the global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. S. Díaz, J. Settele, E. S. Brondízio, H. T. Ngo, M. Guèze, J. Agard, A. Arneth, P. Balvanera, K. A. Brauman, S. H. M. Butchart, K. M. A. Chan, L. A. Garibaldi, K. Ichii, J. Liu, S. M. Subramanian, G. F. Midgley, P. Miloslavich, Z. Molnár, D. Obura, A. Pfaff, S. Polasky, A. Purvis, J. Razzaque, B. Reyers, R. R. Chowdhury, Y. J. Shin, I. J. Visseren-Hamakers, K. J. Willis, & C. N. Zayas (Eds.), (pp. 56). IPBES secretariat.

Jehlička, P., Jacobsson, K., 2021. The importance of recognizing difference: Rethinking Central and East European environmentalism. *Political Geography* 87, 102379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polgeo.2021.102379>

Karcher, D.B., Cvitanovic, C., Colvin, R.M., Van Putten, I.E., Reed, M.S., 2021. Is this what success looks like? Mismatches between the aims, claims, and evidence used to demonstrate impact from knowledge exchange processes at the interface of environmental science and policy. *Environmental Science & Policy* 125, 202–218.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.08.012>

Keenan, R.J., Pozza, G., Fitzsimons, J.A., 2019. Ecosystem services in environmental policy: Barriers and opportunities for increased adoption. *Ecosystem Services* 38, 100943.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.100943>

Luyet, V., Schlaepfer, R., Parlange, M.B., Buttler, A., 2012. A framework to implement Stakeholder participation in environmental projects. *Journal of Environmental Management* 111, 213–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.06.026>

Malmberg, K., Enfors-Kautsky, E., Queiroz, C., Norström, A., Schultz, L., 2021. Operationalizing ecosystem service bundles for strategic sustainability planning: A participatory approach. *Ambio* 50, 314–331. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-020-01378-w>

Mandle, L., Shields-Estrada, A., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Mitchell, M.G.E., Bremer, L.L., Gourevitch, J.D., Hawthorne, P., Johnson, J.A., Robinson, B.E., Smith, J.R., Sonter, L.J., Verutes, G.M., Vogl, A.L., Daily, G.C., Ricketts, T.H., 2020. Increasing decision relevance of ecosystem service science. *Nat Sustain* 4, 161–169. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-00625-y>

Martín-López, B., Felipe-Lucia, M.R., Bennett, E.M., Norström, A., Peterson, G., Plieninger, T., Hicks, C.C., Turkelboom, F., García-Llorente, M., Jacobs, S., Lavorel, S., Locatelli, B., 2019. A novel telecoupling framework to assess social relations across spatial scales for ecosystem services research. *Journal of Environmental Management* 241, 251–263.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.04.029>

Maund, P.R., Irvine, K.N., Dallimer, M., Fish, R., Austen, G.E., Davies, Z.G., 2020. Do ecosystem service frameworks represent people's values? *Ecosystem Services* 46, 101221.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101221>

Metzger, M.J., Dick, J., Gardner, A., Bellamy, C., Blackstock, K., Brown, C., Chisholm, R., Cochrane, P., Drewitt, J., Gimona, A., Hester, A., Mathieson, S., Nijnik, M., McVittie, A., Petr, M., Smith, R., Smith, M., 2019. Knowledge sharing, problem solving and professional development in a Scottish Ecosystem Services Community of Practice. *Reg Environ Change* 19, 2275–2286. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-019-01537-0>

Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MA), 2005. *Ecosystems and human well-being: Synthesis*. Washington, DC: Island Press.

Nastran, M., 2015. Why does nobody ask us? Impacts on local perception of a protected area in designation, Slovenia. *Land Use Policy* 46, 38–49.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2015.02.001>

Nesshöver, C., Vandewalle, M., Wittmer, H., Balian, E.V., Carmen, E., Geizendorffer, I.R., Görg, C., Jongman, R., Livoreil, B., Santamaria, L., Schindler, S., Settele, J., Sousa Pinto, I.,

Török, K., Van Dijk, J., Watt, A.D., Young, J.C., Zulka, K.P., 2016. The Network of Knowledge approach: improving the science and society dialogue on biodiversity and ecosystem services in Europe. *Biodivers Conserv* 25, 1215–1233. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-016-1127-5>

Norström, A.V., Cvitanovic, C., Löf, M.F., West, S., Wyborn, C., Balvanera, P., Bednarek, A.T., Bennett, E.M., Biggs, R., De Bremond, A., Campbell, B.M., Canadell, J.G., Carpenter, S.R., Folke, C., Fulton, E.A., Gaffney, O., Gelcich, S., Jouffray, J.-B., Leach, M., Le Tissier, M., Martín-López, B., Louder, E., Loutre, M.-F., Meadow, A.M., Nagendra, H., Payne, D., Peterson, G.D., Reyers, B., Scholes, R., Speranza, C.I., Spierenburg, M., Stafford-Smith, M., Tengö, M., Van Der Hel, S., Van Putten, I., Österblom, H., 2020. Principles for knowledge co-production in sustainability research. *Nat Sustain* 3, 182–190. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0448-2>

Patenaude, G., Lautenbach, S., Paterson, J.S., Locatelli, T., Dormann, C.F., Metzger, M.J., Walz, A., 2019. Breaking the ecosystem services glass ceiling: realising impact. *Reg Environ Change* 19, 2261–2274. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-018-1434-3>

Posner, S., Getz, C., Ricketts, T., 2016. Evaluating the impact of ecosystem service assessments on decision-makers. *Environmental Science & Policy* 64, 30–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2016.06.003>

Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (Program) (2005) *Ecosystems and human wellbeing: synthesis*. Island Press, Washington, DC.

Raum, S., 2018. A framework for integrating systematic stakeholder analysis in ecosystem services research: Stakeholder mapping for forest ecosystem services in the UK. *Ecosystem Services* 29, 170–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.01.001>

Reed, M.G., Abernethy, P., 2018. Facilitating Co-Production of Transdisciplinary Knowledge for Sustainability: Working with Canadian Biosphere Reserve Practitioners. *Society & Natural Resources* 31, 39–56. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2017.1383545>

Reed, M.S., Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., Prell, C., Quinn, C.H., Stringer, L.C., 2009. Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. *Journal of Environmental Management* 90, 1933–1949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2009.01.001>

Reed, M.S., Stringer, L.C., Fazey, I., Evely, A.C., Kruijssen, J.H.J., 2014. Five principles for the practice of knowledge exchange in environmental management. *Journal of Environmental Management* 146, 337–345. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2014.07.021>

Ruckelshaus, M., McKenzie, E., Tallis, H., Guerry, A., Daily, G., Kareiva, P., Polasky, S., Ricketts, T., Bhagabati, N., Wood, S.A., Bernhardt, J., 2015. Notes from the field: Lessons learned from using ecosystem service approaches to inform real-world decisions. *Ecological Economics* 115, 11–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2013.07.009>

Saarikoski, H., Primmer, E., Saarela, S.-R., Antunes, P., Aszalós, R., Baró, F., Berry, P., Blanco, G.G., Gómez-Baggethun, E., Carvalho, L., Dick, J., Dunford, R., Hanzu, M., Harrison, P.A., Izakovcova, Z., Kertész, M., Kopperoinen, L., Köhler, B., Langemeyer, J., Lapola, D., Liqueste,

C., Luque, S., Mederly, P., Niemelä, J., Palomo, I., Pastur, G.M., Peri, P.L., Preda, E., Priess, J.A., Santos, R., Schleyer, C., Turkelboom, F., Vadineanu, A., Verheyden, W., Vikström, S., Young, J., 2018. Institutional challenges in putting ecosystem service knowledge in practice. *Ecosystem Services* 29, 579–598. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.07.019>

Saldaña, J., 2016. *The coding manual for qualitative researchers*, 3E [Third edition]. ed. SAGE, Los Angeles ; London.

Sarkki, S., Ficko, A., Wielgolaski, F., Abraham, E., Bratanova-Doncheva, S., Grunewald, K., Hofgaard, A., Holtmeier, F., Kyriazopoulos, A., Broll, G., Nijnik, M., Sutinen, M., 2017. Assessing the resilient provision of ecosystem services by social-ecological systems: introduction and theory. *Clim. Res.* 73, 7–15. <https://doi.org/10.3354/cr01437>

Sarkki, S., Tinch, R., Niemelä, J., Heink, U., Waylen, K., Timaeus, J., Young, J., Watt, A., Nesshöver, C., Van Den Hove, S., 2015. Adding 'iterativity' to the credibility, relevance, legitimacy: A novel scheme to highlight dynamic aspects of science–policy interfaces. *Environmental Science & Policy* 54, 505–512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.02.016>

Scemama, P., Mongruel, R., Kermagoret, C., Bailly, D., Carlier, A., Mao, P.L., Vaschalde, E.D., 2022. Guidance for stakeholder consultation to support national ecosystem services assessment: A case study from French marine assessment. *Ecosystem Services* 54, 101408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2022.101408>

Schaefer, M., Goldman, E., Bartuska, A.M., Sutton-Grier, A., Lubchenco, J., 2015. Nature as capital: Advancing and incorporating ecosystem services in United States federal policies and programs. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 112, 7383–7389. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1420500112>

Schleyer, C., Lux, A., Mehring, M., Görg, C., 2017. Ecosystem Services as a Boundary Concept: Arguments from Social Ecology. *Sustainability* 9, 1107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9071107>

Schneider, J., Kubíčková, H., 2020. The State of the Art of Use of the Concept of Ecosystem Services within Spatial Plans in the Czech Republic. *Sustainability* 12, 9000. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219000>

Schoonover, H.A., Grêt-Regamey, A., Metzger, M.J., Ruiz-Frau, A., Santos-Reis, M., Scholte, S.S.K., Walz, A., Nicholas, K.A., 2019. Creating space, aligning motivations, and building trust: a practical framework for stakeholder engagement based on experience in 12 ecosystem services case studies. *E&S* 24, art11. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10061-240111>

Slovák, Ľ., Daněk, J., Daněk, T., 2023. The use of focus groups in cultural ecosystem services research: a systematic review. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun* 10, 45. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01530-3>

Spangenberg, J.H., Görg, C., Settele, J., 2015. Stakeholder involvement in ESS research and governance: Between conceptual ambition and practical experiences – risks, challenges and tested tools. *Ecosystem Services* 16, 201–211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2015.10.006>

Straus, S.E., Tetroe, J.M., Graham, I.D., 2011. Knowledge translation is the use of knowledge in health care decision making. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 64, 6–10.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2009.08.016>

Stringer, L.C., Paavola, J., 2013. Participation in environmental conservation and protected area management in Romania: A review of three case studies. *Envir. Conserv.* 40, 138–146.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0376892913000039>

Wagner, N., Sarkki, S., Dietz, T., 2024. More than policy neutral: Justifying the power of science-policy interfaces through legitimacy. *Earth System Governance* 21, 100219.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2024.100219>

Wenger, E., McDermott, R. and Snyder, W., 2002. *Cultivating Communities of Practice: A Guide to Managing Knowledge*. Cambridge, MA, Harvard Business School Press.

Wright, W.C.C., Eppink, F.V., Greenhalgh, S., 2017. Are ecosystem service studies presenting the right information for decision making? *Ecosystem Services* 25, 128–139.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.03.002>

Young, J.C., Rose, D.C., Mumby, H.S., Benitez-Capistros, F., Derrick, C.J., Finch, T., Garcia, C., Home, C., Marwaha, E., Morgans, C., Parkinson, S., Shah, J., Wilson, K.A., Mukherjee, N., 2018. A methodological guide to using and reporting on interviews in conservation science research. *Methods Ecol Evol* 9, 10–19. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12828>

Zolyomi, A., Franklin, A., Smith, B., Soliev, I., 2023. Ecosystem services as the silver bullet? A systematic review of how ecosystem services assessments impact biodiversity prioritisation in policy. *Earth System Governance* 16, 100178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2023.100178>